

Analysis of Fiksimini Community Movement in Cyberspace by Mohammad Rokib

Alya Maulidia Hanum
AquaCulture – IPB University
alyahm123@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of the paper analysis is The rapid development of Information Technology has made Indonesia create a new space in the world of literature. Variety of literary works are abundant and incarnated in new forms in the cyber world. Literary works form their own image with the design of a new genre that transcends space as the "Fiksimini" community movement. This paper uses a descriptive method in an effort to create a community of fiction mini on social networks and websites.

Keywords: *Cyber space, Fiksimini community, literature work*

INTRODUCTION

Cyber literature has become a polemic in Indonesia since the late 1990s. Media publications were initially limited to books, magazines, and newspapers that went through various improvement stages. Over time, the publication of literary works began to shift to cyber media that could be read by the public in a hurry. The existence of a new realm in publishing literary works gives birth to a variety of expressions that form a new "culture" in the work.

Along with the development of cyber media, the emergence of social networks is adding new stretches of literary space in the cyber world. The reality of the development of literature in Indonesia in the cyber world invites two debates, namely the pros and cons. In the stages of development of the pros and cons of the future of literature in cyberspace, cyber literature finds itself in a new world, namely as a forum for new expressions in literature.

METHOD

This study of analysis uses a descriptive qualitative method because it explains a social event for how the writer us for analyzing the paper. This method is seen by the writer to be very important because this method will show a form of explanation related to a phenomenon that is interpreted in the context and concept of writing. Of course, in carrying out this research, the author uses a hermeneutic

approach because this paper analysis will be studied by exegesis of the contents and adjusting to the events that occurred at that time. Social networks bridge literary ideas that can be communicated flexibly. In addition, the interaction between senior and novice writers can be done openly. A work that is not just a short adapted on social networks, but the perfection of a fiction.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings in this study are Fiksimini shows the shortness of a fiction when compared to other fiction. Although the number of sentences and words is short, readers can understand the implied message in the fiction. The advantage of this form of fiction is that it can be read by anyone at any time.

Readers also do not need to bring fiction books because fiction is presented cyber. Readers can enjoy it on their mobile phone or computer. Fiction also creates short literary activities.

The purpose of a this analysis of papers in the form of discussions are parallel as well as balance with technological developments that facilitate human activities. Writers and writers tend to be adaptive to these developments. This power is considered to have eroded a writer in the literary medium.

Whereas the difference between literature as a goal and as a medium lies in the value of literature. Social networks that can bind certain communities have the potential to refresh the literary world. This technological sophistication places literature as if it were a production that necessitated a consumption culture.

CONCLUSION

In general, the fictional community has made a new move in the world of literature. Adjustment and balancing the demands of the development of the electronic world on literature. Fiction is able to create a new spirit and color in literature through the role of technology.

REFERENCES

- Altman, R. (2021). 3. A Semantic/Syntactic Approach to film genre. In *Film genre reader IV* (pp. 27-41). University of Texas Press.
- Barus, I. R. G., Simanjuntak, M. B., & Resmayasari, I. (2021). READING LITERACIES THROUGH EVIETA-BASED LEARNING MATERIAL: STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS (Study Case Taken from Vocational School—IPB University). *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 4(1), 15-20.
- Bateman, J., & Schmidt, K. H. (2013). *Multimodal film analysis: How films mean*. Routledge.

- Bednarek, M. (2015). Corpus-assisted multimodal discourse analysis of television and film narratives. In *Corpora and discourse studies* (pp. 63-87). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Bellour, R. (2000). *The analysis of film*. Indiana University Press.
- Benshoff, H. (2015). *Film and television analysis: An introduction to methods, theories, and approaches*. Routledge.
- Bernadtua, M., Rafli, Z., & Boeriswati, E. (2022, January). LANGUAGES ACQUISITION AND TEACHING IN KELAPA GADING–NORTH JAKARTA (CASE STUDY TAKEN AT SAINT PETER’S JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL). In *UICELL Conference Proceeding* (pp. 162-170).
- Bittau, F., Potamialis, C., Togay, M., Abbas, A., Isherwood, P. J., Bowers, J. W., & Walls, J. M. (2018). Analysis and optimisation of the glass/TCO/MZO stack for thin film CdTe solar cells. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 187, 15-22.
- Carr, D. (2019). Methodology, representation, and games. *Games and Culture*, 14(7-8), 707-723.
- Condon, W. S., & Ogston, W. D. (1966). Sound film analysis of normal and pathological behavior patterns. *Journal of nervous and mental disease*.
- Estrada, L. M., Hielscher, E., Koolen, M., Olesen, C. G., Noordegraaf, J., & Blom, J. (2017). Film analysis as annotation: Exploring current tools. *Moving Image: The Journal of the Association of Moving Image Archivists*, 17(2), 40-70.
- Franco, A., Magnani, A., & Maio, D. (2020). A multimodal approach for human activity recognition based on skeleton and RGB data. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 131, 293-299.
- Geiger, J., & Rutsky, R. L. (Eds.). (2013). *Film analysis: A Norton reader*. WW Norton & Company.
- Henseler, C. (2021). Finding Humanity. *The Scholar as Human: Research and Teaching for Public Impact*, 129.
- Jahn, M. (2003). A guide to narratological film analysis. *Poems, Plays, and Prose: A Guide to the Theory of Literary Genres*, 2.
- Kendrick, M. (2016). *Literacy and multimodality across global sites*. Routledge.
- Kozlarek, O. (2015). Introduction: Crossing Borders, Reaching Humanity. In *Octavio Paz* (pp. 9-16). transcript-Verlag.
- Liu, A. A., Xu, N., Nie, W. Z., Su, Y. T., Wong, Y., & Kankanhalli, M. (2016). Benchmarking a multimodal and multiview and interactive dataset for human action recognition. *IEEE Transactions on cybernetics*, 47(7), 1781-1794.
- Lo, H. F., Wu, I. W., & Ni, C. C. (2018, July). Representation of Memory in Design for Humanity. In *International Conference on Cross-Cultural Design* (pp. 43-57). Springer, Cham.

- Magnusson, P., & Godhe, A. L. (2019). Multimodality in Language Education--Implications for Teaching. *Designs for Learning*, 11(1), 127-137.
- Parc, J. (2018). Evaluating the effects of protectionism on the film industry: A case study analysis of Korea. In *Handbook of State Aid for Film* (pp. 349-366). Springer, Cham.
- Pattiwael, A. S. (2019). Literature for Developing Student's Humanity Awareness. In *Journal International Seminar on Languages, Literature, Arts, and Education (ISLLAE)* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 79-88).
- Peña-Cervel, M. S. (2016). Motivating film title translation: a cognitive analysis. *CÍRCULO de Lingüística Aplicada a la Comunicación*, 66, 31.
- Plate, L. (2015). How to do things with literature in the digital age: Anne Carson's *Nox*, multimodality, and the ethics of bookishness. *Contemporary Women's Writing*, 9(1), 93-111.
- Richards, M. (2016). Film Music Themes: Analysis and Corpus Study. *Music Theory Online*, 22(1).
- Rosenberg, F. J. (2016). *After Human Rights: Literature, Visual Arts, and Film in Latin America, 1990-2010*. University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Rouast, P. V., Adam, M. T., & Chiong, R. (2019). Deep learning for human affect recognition: Insights and new developments. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, 12(2), 524-543.
- Santos, R. B., & de Oliveira, U. R. (2019). Analysis of occupational risk management tools for the film and television industry. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 72, 199-211.
- Serafini, F. (2015). Multimodal literacy: From theories to practices. *Language Arts*, 92(6), 412-423.
- Simanjuntak, M. B. (2021). METAMORPHIC ANALYSIS IN SONG LYRICS BATAK TOBA "AUT BOI NIAN" WRITTEN BY WERVIN PANGGABEAN. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 4(1), 34-39.
- Simanjuntak, M. B. , Suseno, M., Ramdhoni, R., Mayuni, I. , Zuriyati, Z., & Sutrisno, S. (2022). The Value of Parents' Image in Seven Batak Toba Songs (Literary Art Study). *Jurnal Pendidikan Tambusai*, 6(2), 8540–8551.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., & Barus, I. R. G. (2020). English Reading Literacies to Improve Values Among Teenagers. *SELTICS*, 93-102.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., & Lumingkewas, M. S. (2022). THE WOMAN IN THE BOOK OF KINGS (LITERARY STUDIES AND HERMENEUTICS). In *UICELL Conference Proceeding* (pp. 328-334).
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Barus, I. R. G., & Resmayasari, I. (2021). ANALYSIS OF VIOLENCE IN CITY OF GOD FILM DIRECTED BY FERNANDO MEIRELLES. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 4(1), 1-6.

- Simanjuntak, M. B., Barus, I. R. G., & Resmayasari, I. (2021). Analysis of Song" Tanganku Na Metmet" by Using Translation Techniques into English. In *UICELL Conference Proceeding* (pp. 195-202).
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Lumingkewas, M. S., & Sutrisno, S. (2021). ANALYSIS OF TANGIANG ALE AMANAMI (OUR FATHER) USING THE TECHNIQUES OF TRANSLATION. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 4(2), 70-75.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Rahmat, A. ., Setiadi, S. ., Suseno, M. ., Romdani, R., & Lumingkewas, M. S. . (2022). Power Relations in the Story of “Nommensen Bertemu Raja Panggalamei” by Patar Pasaribu. *Jurnal Pendidikan Tambusai*, 6(2), 8552–8557.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Suseno, M., & Setiadi, S. (2022). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MICROSOFT OFFICE 365 AS AN ONLINE ENGLISH LEARNING MEDIA. In *UICELL Conference Proceeding* (pp. 25-32).
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Suseno, M., Setiadi, S., Lustyantie, N., & Barus, I. R. G. R. G. (2022). Integration of Curricula (Curriculum 2013 and Cambridge Curriculum for Junior High School Level in Three Subjects) in Pandemic Situation. *Ideas: Jurnal Pendidikan, Sosial, dan Budaya*, 8(1), 77-86.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Sutrisno, S., & Lumingkewas, M. S. (2021). LITERARY STUDY “NOMMENSEN, APOSTLE IN BATAKNESE”. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 4(2), 42-45.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Zuriyati, Z., & Lustyantie, N. (2022). METAMORPHIC ANALYSIS IN SONG LYRICS BATAK TOBA “JUJUNG GOARHI AMANG”(STUDY OF PORTRAY OF PARENTS). *PROJECT (Professional Journal of English Education)*, 5(1), 236-243.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Zuriyati, Z., Utami, S. R., & Lumingkewas, M. S. (2022). Nommensen and Bataknese (The Representation of Apostle). *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal): Humanities and Social Sciences*, 5(2), 9291-9297.
- Sleman, S. M., & Fahmi, I. M. (2020). The Destiny of Humanity in the Future Cities of Ray Bradbury. *Zanco Journal of Humanity Sciences*, 24(1), 278-288.
- Teixeira, M. B. M., da Costa Galvao, L. L., Mota-Santos, C. M., & Carmo, L. J. O. (2020). Women and work: film analysis of Most Beautiful Thing. *Revista de Gestão*.
- Way, L. C., & McKerrell, S. (2017). *Music as multimodal discourse: Semiotics, power and protest*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Wellek, R. (2018). *The attack on literature and other essays*. UNC Press Books.
- Widjayanti, E. P. (2019). Building Humanity Values Through Maya Angelou's poems. In *Journal International Seminar on Languages, Literature, Arts, and Education (ISLLAE)* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 143-148).
- Wildfeuer, J. (2014). *Film discourse interpretation: Towards a new paradigm for multimodal film analysis*. Routledge.

Wu, J., & Yan, Y. (2016, November). Study of humanity teaching model in higher vocational school Chinese teaching. In *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Management Science, Education Tecnology, Arts, Social Science and Economics* (Vol. 85, pp. 1855-1858).